

Simulating Exoplanetary Atmospheres in the Laboratory: Current capabilities of the Berlin Atmospheric Simulation Experiments (BASE) Chamber

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Abstract

In recent years, the remarkable progress in exoplanet science has unveiled a stunning diversity of exoplanets, whereby technological advancements have significantly expanded our capacity to investigate planetary objects beyond our solar system. These bodies exhibit very diverse properties, including their sizes, compositions, and orbital characteristics. Understanding the complex chemical-climate responses occurring in their atmospheres plays a pivotal role with regard to potential habitability and much work is still required in this field. To interpret forthcoming spectra obtained from exoplanetary atmospheres, there is a concerted effort to model these worlds. However, model parameters are often inferred from limited data sets. Consequently, laboratory-based atmospheric simulations are much needed to increase our understanding of complex gas-phase interactions and to provide input parameters for atmospheric models. In this paper we present the new Berlin Atmospheric Simulation Experiments (BASE) chamber, show current capabilities and give an overview of experimental scenarios with applications ranging from planetary objects (e.g. Mars, Venus, Titan) in the solar system to Earth-like exoplanets.

Keywords: Atmospheric simulation chamber, gas-phase reactions, photochemistry, atmospheric modeling, biosignatures, habitability, exoplanets

1. Introduction

Understanding the universe around us has always been a captivating pursuit for humanity, igniting our curiosity about the possibility of life existing beyond our home planet. In recent years, the remarkable progress in exoplanet discoveries has brought us closer to answering this age-old question. We now know that exoplanets, planets orbiting stars outside our solar system, are incredibly diverse in terms of their sizes, compositions, and orbital characteristics [1], [2]. For instance, new classes including hot Jupiters [3], [4], [5],[6], mini-Neptunes [7], [8], [9] and super Earths have been discovered and extensively studied [10]. These classes of exoplanets lack counterparts within our own solar system. Excitingly, among the several thousand exoplanets discovered so far [11], some rocky planets in the habitable zone (HZ) of their star have been detected [12], [13],[14], [15]. Planetary atmospheres likely play a pivotal role in shaping their potential habitability. While significant efforts have been made to identify rocky exoplanets and characterise their physical properties, understanding the complex chemistry occurring in their atmospheres remains an ongoing challenge.

For modern Earth's atmosphere, chemical networks have been studied in detail both in the atmosphere directly [16], [17], [18], [19] ,[20] or in dedicated atmospheric simulation chambers (A non-exhaustive list of facilities within Europe is given

on www.eurochamp.org). The range of topics that have been addressed includes the oxygen-ozone cycle and other gas-phase chemistry [21], understanding oxidative capacity [22], secondary organic aerosol formation and growth [23], along with studies of the cryosphere, air-sea exchange and real-world emissions [24] , [25]. Ongoing efforts extend the comparison of laboratory experiments with atmospheric models to other planetary object such as Mars [26], [27] or Titan [28].

Regarding exoplanets, there is a pending need for theoretical and experimental atmospheric and astrochemistry studies [4]. Ongoing missions such as TESS [29], CHEOPS [30] and JWST [31] as well as forthcoming missions such as PLATO [32] and ARIEL [33] are delivering / will deliver exciting new data, which requires a new generation of flexible, physically consistent photochemical-climate models to interpret. However, as these distant worlds often have no counterpart in the solar system, and since there will be no in-situ data, this process requires careful comparison with planetary simulation chambers. Such chambers recreate exoplanetary atmospheric conditions in order to interpret atmospheric biosignature responses and assess the potential for habitability. In particular it is fundamental to understand alteration of potential gaseous biomarkers and their distinction from potential abiotic sources [34]. Regarding biosignatures, Grenfell et al.[35] reviewed the range of possible responses on rocky exoplanets. Important factors include

the incoming stellar spectrum, the atmospheric mass and composition as well as the role of clouds and surface properties. Favored targets include rocky planets orbiting in the habitable zone of cooler stars as reviewed in Shields et al.[36]. For such worlds, however, high energy particles (HEPs) from strong stellar flares can generate secondary electrons which can greatly influence biosignature abundances as investigated by e.g. Grenfell et al.[37] and Herbst et al.[38]. Yet many atmospheric simulation chambers lack simultaneous photon and electron irradiation capabilities.

Clouds and hazes are central features of exoplanetary atmospheres as reviewed in Helling et al. [39]. An improved understanding of the microphysical processes affecting clouds (see e.g. review by Seinfeld [40]), as well as their chemical and thermal stability in reactive exoplanet environments, is crucial to make sense of future spectroscopic data from exoplanets [41]. Further research is needed, including both theoretical and observational kinetic studies of chemical processes involved in gas-to-particle conversion and heterogeneous gas-particle reactions, as well as determining vapor pressures of refractory materials to estimate the formation of condensate clouds.

In this paper, we present the new Berlin Atmospheric Simulation Experiments (BASE) chamber at Freie Universitaet Berlin. BASE is an experimental set-up built to simulate various atmospheric layers, including pressure, temperature and gas composition of Earth-like objects in the solar system and beyond. With BASE we will study photochemical processes driven by UV and Lyman alpha radiation, as well as via impinging electrons, which are present in air shower events. Our facility allows the continuous spectroscopic real-time monitoring of gas samples across a wide wavelength range as well as simultaneous mass spectrometric analysis.

We expect to provide valuable insights in understanding complex chemical pathways for a range of reasonable Earth-like atmospheres, ranging from primary and steam (Early Earth) to thin, cool Mars-like up to thick, hot Venus-like, which not only improve current atmospheric models but aid in the definition of a set of reliable and detectable biomarkers in exoplanet atmospheres.

2. Facility description

The new simulation chamber is based on a cylindrical, customised 304L stainless steel vacuum chamber with a height of 10 cm and an inner diameter of 20 cm. The 3D CAD drawing is available upon request. Multiple high-vacuum-compatible connections, interfacing various analytical instruments, are evenly distributed over the surface of the main cylinder. The whole set-up is placed inside a glovebox to minimise oxygen and water contamination and to ensure a constant nitrogen purge of the measurement systems (e.g. pathways of spectrometers). BASE is designed for laboratory simulations of atmospheric processes on habitable planets and planetary objects. Scenarios over a wide pressure range starting at atmospheric pressures of 1-1.5 bar (e.g. modern Earth or Titan's surface) down to a few mbar (e.g. Mars or Earth's upper stratosphere) or below are feasible. Prior to any experiment the chamber is regularly

baked and evacuated at a minimum background pressure as low as $5 \cdot 10^{-9}$ mbar for several hours to days. Experiments that aim to study atmospheric conditions within the pressure range of 1 bar to a few mbar can be conducted using BASE in a static mode. Here the chamber is pumped to the minimum pressure, disconnected from the pump by a gate valve and replenished by a given atmospheric gas composition up to a required pressure. Alternatively, for lower pressure scenarios, BASE can be used in a dynamic mode, where the pumping speed and a constant gas flow into the chamber are regulated to reach any equilibrium pressure from 1 bar down to $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ mbar.

Figure 1: Sketch of the BASE chamber including irradiation sources and analytical instruments. Irradiation sources: (EG) Electron gun, (FL) Flowlamp, (SoSi) Solarsimulator, (VUV) Hydrogen Helium lamp; Measurement instruments: (IR) FT-IR spectroscopy, (VUV) VUV spectroscopy, (UV/VIS) UV/VIS spectroscopy, (QMS) Quadrupole massspectrometry, (P) Pressure gauge

The main chamber is attached to a custom built gas mixing system. The mixing chamber holds a volume of one liter and can be simultaneously filled by up to four inlets via digitally controlled, calibrated flow meters. It enables the in-house mixing of various atmospheric gas compositions, including the addition of water vapour in a user-defined amount. In the static mode BASE is directly filled with a premixed composition from the mixing chamber. In the dynamic mode, the throughput of the flow meters are set such that the gas composition of the main chamber remains constant. This highly flexible, modular design reflects the demand to model the very different atmospheric conditions found on planetary objects.

The current set-up further provides a heating option, setting the working temperature to any value between 293K and 373K. These temperatures are compatible with water existing in liquid form, which is an essential condition for potential habitability.

2.0.1. Irradiation sources

In order to trigger complex photochemical processes, atmospheric mixtures can be exposed to different radiation sources

covering the VUV, including Lyman alpha, to NIR range, as well as particle radiation.

The continuous spectral UV/VIS/NIR irradiation is provided by either of two tunable solar simulators (300 W and 150W). Each of which can be run with different light sources and combined with a variety of air mass filters (AM0, AM1 and AM1.5) and IR water filters. Available light sources include standard Xenon short arc lamps with different coatings (Ushio, UXL-302-0, Hamamatsu L2479) and a mercury enhanced Xenon short arc lamp (Hamamatsu, L2483). Their spectra not only differ in their gas-specific features but also in the relative number of UV to Vis photons in the continuum. The standard xenon light bulb has a special coating to suppress photochemical ozone production, while the spectrum of the others are explicitly ozone producing.

Additional high energy VUV photons can be added with a windowless, reverse flow excitation plasma lamp providing photons in the sub 120 nm range. To initiate the plasma, the pressure at the tip of the lamp must be lower than $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mbar, limiting the possible pressure inside the chamber to the sub $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mbar range. In order to use the flow lamp with higher atmospheric pressures, either a differential pumping system or a magnesium fluoride window must be introduced. In typical experiments, unless there is a known photochemical process for which sub 120 nm photons are required, the lamp is used together with a window for simplicity. Finally, a hydrogen-helium lamp is used to provide a stable continuum in the deep UV as well as the scientifically interesting Lyman-alpha photons at 121 nm.

The combination of the three light sources (Solarsimulator, Flow lamp, HHe Lamp) allows the simulation of very different irradiation spectra from 120 - 800 nm. Figure (2) shows the spectrum of the three light sources for a typical experiment. Each light source has been absolutely calibrated using two NIST standard sources for fidelity.

Figure 2: Irradiance of available light sources. Gray Area: Solar simulator with a standard xenon short arc lamp (Ushio, UXL-302-O). Black Line: Solar simulator with a ozone producing Mercury enhanced xenon short arc lamp (Hamamatsu, L2483). Yellow area: HHe lamp (Resonance) providing a stable continuum in the deep UV, including Lyman-alpha photons at 121 nm. Red Line: Spectrum of the flow lamp (Resonance) used with nitrogen gas at a pressure of $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mbar.

Additionally, the chamber also includes particle radiation from an electron source (Specs Group, EQ 22/35). Key atmospheric species typically undergo electronic dissociation with impacting electron energies lower than a few hundred eV. On Earth, secondary electrons with these energies are typically absorbed above the mesosphere although such particles could maybe penetrate to lower altitudes for planets in the close-in HZ of high flare activity cool stars [42]. The electron gun provides a single electron energy in the range of 20 eV to 5 keV and a current of 100 uA. The maximal working pressure of the device is $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mbar, and hence a differential pumping system is typically required, similar to the flow lamp in windowless mode. Electron irradiation experiments are performed in equivalent dose mode. The output spectrum of the electron gun is highly monochromatic with a spread of less than 1 eV around a user defined value. The source therefore falls short in simultaneously producing the full electron energy spectrum found in Earth's atmosphere but provides an equivalent dose. The dose supplied to the chamber during any given experiment is measured in two ways. The first is with a retractable Faraday cup inserted into the chamber connected to a Keithley picoammeter. The second is using Gafchromic EBT3 films and a calibrated scanning system.

2.1. Measurement techniques

The BASE chamber offers various real time measurement techniques such as VUV, UV/VIS and FT-IR absorption spectroscopy, quadrupole mass spectrometry and gas specific electro-chemical sensors.

For VUV absorption spectroscopy a calibrated VUV spectrograph (Resonance Ltd.) is directly connected to the main chamber opposite to the Hydrogen Helium lamp. The spectral range starts at 120 nm, given by the cut-off of an internal MgF_2 window, up to 340 nm with a resolution of 0.15 nm. The integration time can be set to any value between 6 ms and 166 min.

The fiber-based UV/Vis Spectrometer (Ocean Optics) covers the spectral range from 200 nm to 850 nm with a resolution of 1.3 nm. The source is a calibrated deuterium and/or calibrated halogen lamp, connected to UV enhanced fibers, minimizing the loss of photons towards the UV range. The fibers are connected to lenses, which are attached on the outside of two fused silicate windows and aligned opposite of each other. Restraining from the use of fiber feedthroughs not only minimizes the leak rate but allows realignment without opening the BASE chamber.

The beam of the IR spectrometer (ArcOptix) is relayed through the gas sample using parabolic mirrors. Passing two CaF_2 windows the instrument measures in a spectral range from 830 cm^{-1} to 5000 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 1 cm^{-1} . Given by the construction of the instrument several centimeter of the beam pass the outside of the chamber. To prevent measurements of the gas sample inside the BASE chamber from interference with infrared active species in the surrounding (e.g. H_2O , CO_2), BASE is placed inside a glove box. Moreover, the high amount of oxygen in air makes it experimentally challenging to simulate anoxic atmospheres. Therefore placing the set-

up in a dry, infrared inactive (e.g. N_2 or Ar) environment is not only crucial for the spectroscopic measurements but further decreases potential contamination of atmospheric mixtures by diffusion through the stainless steel.

Besides the spectroscopic analysis the gas is sampled with a compact quadrupole mass spectrometer. The open ions source consists of two Y_2O_3 filaments. The Faraday detector and the secondary electron multiplier (SEM) offer a dynamic measurement range from 1-300 amu with a resolution of 1 amu. The detection limit of any species is $1 \cdot 10^{-12}$ mbar. To account for small pressure changes during experiments the mass spectrum data is normalised to the total ion count (TIC). Therefore, by measuring the total pressure inside the chamber, the partial pressure of different species can be calculated.

While the spectroscopy techniques can be used independent from the pressure inside the chamber, the mass spectrometer has a working pressure below $5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mbar. Similar to the electron gun this limitation can be circumvented by using a differential pumping system, which allows the continuous sampling of the gas mixtures independent of the pressure inside the BASE main chamber.

3. Limitations of atmospheric simulation chambers

Chamber science is confronted with a number of experimental challenges including, but not limited to, physical dimensions and material of the simulation chamber, potential contamination, detection thresholds and working pressures of analytical instruments, generation of synthetic radiation spectra and Health and Safety regulations for different gaseous species. Consequently, experimental configurations are often fine-tuned to specific scenarios, balancing the technical constraints with the required specification to answer scientific questions.

3.1. Surface-to-Volume Ratio, Wall Loss and Leak Rate

Atmospheric simulation chambers have a notable drawback in the form of walls, which inevitably lead to the loss of gases throughout an experiment. These losses are directly linked to wall-promoted processes. Consequently, when using modeling as a tool to interpret chamber experiments, it becomes crucial to incorporate loss processes into the chemical schemes at appropriate rates. The significance of these heterogeneous effects has been recognised since the early days of chamber usage [43]. However, there is limited data available on the rates of organic and inorganic compound losses in environmental chambers [44]. These losses can act as a competing pathway for the consumption of important molecules or as an additional sink preventing the condensation of semi-volatile products onto the aerosol phase. Therefore, it is crucial to carefully evaluate the extent of these effects, which depend on the chemical nature of the species involved and includes various processes such as adsorption, condensation, or reactive uptake. It is important to note that these parameters are highly influenced by chamber history, material and operating conditions, such as temperature and relative humidity. In order to minimize the influence of wall effects, the Surface-to-Volume ratio (SVR) of chambers

are kept as small as possible. However, it is important to note that this ratio is often constrained by external factors such as spatial limitation and material of the chamber. For example, large Teflon tents provide a highly favorable SVR but with the cost of additional HONO release from the wall under irradiation [45] or the absence of temperature and pressure control. Alternatively, more robust chambers, such as those constructed from stainless steel, might provide better contamination control, but often suffer from smaller detection limits, imposed by spatial constraints for analytical instrumentation or simply the amount of gas sample available for examination [44]. Therefore, quantification needs to be performed on a case-by-case basis, and relevant test experiments should accompany each series of studies. Whenever possible, deriving these parameters for reactants from a "dark period" preceding each experiment is preferable.

In order to provide insight into the behavior of chamber walls and their magnitude, we show the first order wall loss for two species measured by BASE. To show the very different behaviour two experiments have been conducted using a "sticky" species (ozone) and a long-lived one (methane).

Prior to the experiments the chamber was heated (373K) and evacuated for several days to remove possible contamination. Next, a known concentration of methane was introduced into the chamber and tracked over the time span of two weeks by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR). The FT-IR analysis showed no significant wall loss for methane. We therefore only give an upper bound for the dry deposition rate of methane of $1.35 \cdot 10^{-7} \frac{cm}{s}$, corresponding to a half life or around 42 days. Given that most of the experiments have a running time of several days to weeks, the wall loss of methane is therefore a minor effect. Over the duration of the experiment the pressure inside the BASE chamber rose from $2.66 \cdot 10^{-1}$ mbar to 1.08 mbar, which corresponds to an overall leak rate of $3.4 \cdot 10^{-7} \frac{l\ mbar}{s}$ in the given configuration.

Ozone, being a highly reactive molecule, was generated inside the chamber via UV photolysis of oxygen in synthetic air (Lindegas). Upon deactivation of the light source, the accumulating ozone concentration was subsequently quantified using a UV/VIS spectrometer. The first-order total wall loss rate is calculated from a linear fit on a semi-logarithmic plot, yielding a value of $-5.5481 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$ ($R^2 = 0.9856$). This corresponds to a dry deposition rate of $2.7 \times 10^{-3} \frac{cm}{s}$ and a half life of approx. 30 min for ozone inside our chamber. Cape et al. [46] report a very similar deposition rate for stainless steel in their chamber at room temperature. Interestingly they did not find any significant dependence on relative humidity, where McClurkin et al. [47] report a dependence on several parameters including relative humidity, air velocity, temperature.

3.2. Limits for gas mixing

When working with exoplanetary atmospheres in the laboratory, Earth's atmosphere is a persistent source of contamination. In particular, the simulation of anoxic gas mixtures is a major experimental challenge. Highly reactive oxygen (O) and hydroxyl (OH) radicals, which readily form through the irradiation of oxygen or water impurities inside the chamber, have

Figure 3: First order wall loss measurement for a non-reactive (Methane) and "sticky" species (Ozone) measured with BASE. Top: Normalised methane concentration inside the BASE chamber over a duration of two weeks. Due to the very low loss rate of methane, we only provide a worst-case scenario upper bound on the wall loss rate. Bottom: Normalised ozone concentration as a function of time measured with the UV/VIS spectrometer

the potential to strongly impact the chemical reactions that take place. Sample contamination is effectively mitigated through the implementation of regular cleaning protocols, while the diffusion of substances through the chamber walls is suppressed by the controlled environment inside the glovebox. Gas samples constituents must be in accordance with Health and Safety regulations. To ensure the precise control of volume mixing ratios (vmr) within gas mixtures, calibrated flow meters are used, providing a minimum volume mixing ratio of 0.0002 for any species. Caution must be taken during the actual mixing process. Flow meters are calibrated for a particular gas species at a given input pressure. Therefore, flow rates must be adjusted and corrected for different gases introduced during the mixing procedure. Similar considerations may apply to pressure measurements and gas-specific sensors. Correction coefficients are referenced from lookup tables for commonly-investigated gas species or must be calibrated for more exotic ones.

3.3. Limits for irradiation

The synthetic generation of the real solar spectrum poses a notable technical challenge. In the context of solar panel testing substantial efforts are directed toward replicating the solar spectrum received on Earth's surface, but available light sources often fall short in accurately matching the real solar spectrum particularly in the infrared (IR) and ultraviolet (UV) range. For gas-phase chemistry, the UV range is of particular interest, given its capacity to trigger photochemical reactions. Unfortunately, many materials, such as plastics and glasses, exhibit a strong absorption towards shorter wavelengths. In experiments necessitating photons with wavelengths below 120 nm, experimental configurations must incorporate windowless sources, a constraint that often limits such experiments to low-pressure scenarios. Alternatively, configurations for higher pressure scenarios, necessitate adaptation, frequently using a differential pumping system.

The endeavor to simulate not only photon radiation but also particle radiation in the laboratory is more difficult. Replicating a typical particle energy spectrum as they occur in Earth's atmosphere, in particular, is currently unfeasible. Experiments that use particle accelerators to investigate the interaction of gases with heavy ions are both costly and require ultra high vacuum. Electron radiation can be included by electron sources such as electron guns. These are relatively compact and lightweight instruments that are available in a variety of configurations, offering practical utility across a wide range of applications. In the context of atmospheric interactions with cosmic rays, it is the secondary electrons that are assumed to play a pivotal role and therefore scientifically justifies the use of an electron gun. Nevertheless these instruments do not provide a particle spectra and experiments can only be conducted in equivalent dose mode.

3.4. Limits for analytical methods

3.4.1. Spectroscopy

The investigation of gas-phase reactions using transmission spectroscopy offers notable advantages over other analytical techniques. On the one hand, instruments are available in diverse configurations, affording a wide range of practical applications. Simultaneously, from a scientific standpoint, they offer a highly species-specific measurement. On the other hand, experimental limits are imposed by either the time resolution or the concentration of the species of interest itself. Particularly in low pressure scenarios, detection limits are notably lower, as the absorption is directly proportional to the concentration of the gas species along the beam path. A possible strategy to compensate for lower concentrations is to elongate the path length, often achieved through the use of mirrors or so called white cells. Additionally, in the context of gas mixtures, overlapping cross-sections may induce further experimental constraints, such as low absorbance of trace gases in a spectral region that is dominated by the main component of the atmosphere. Depending on the instrument, the optical path often extends several centimeters beyond the chamber, potentially introducing absorption features from the surroundings. Hence, it is crucial to ensure a highly stable background or, as is the case of the

Species	Detection Limit
O_2	5 ppb
O_3	8 ppm
H_2O	5 ppm
CH_4	6 ppm
CO_2	1.5 ppm
CO (*)	15 ppb
NO_2 (*)	15 ppm

Table 1: List of species measured at BASE and spectroscopic detection limits for a 1 bar scenario. (*) Estimated values based on comparison with the listed absorption cross section for CO_2

BASE chamber, the entire experimental set-up is placed inside a glovebox, filled with a non-IR active gas such as nitrogen or argon.

3.4.2. Mass spectrometry

The mass spectrometer collects gas samples directly from the interior of the chamber. The working pressure of such a device is below $5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mbar, limiting the experiments to lower pressure scenarios. Alternatively the set-up must be modified to incorporate a differential pumping system when dealing with higher pressure conditions. Note that the constant sampling results in a depletion of gas within the chamber, which must either be replenished or compensated for during the data analysis process. The absolute detection limit for a single species is $1 \cdot 10^{-12}$ mbar inside the chamber. That being said, within a gas mixture the minimum concentration for an individual species must be above 10 ppm to be detectable. This limitation is given by the sensor of the mass spectrometer, that can reliably resolve concentration over a range of five orders of magnitude. Similar to previously mentioned spectroscopy techniques, in mass spectrometry individual species exhibit unique fragmentation patterns. Sampling gas mixtures, this may lead to an overlap of several species at specific mass-to-charge ratio. For example, single ionized methane and double ionized oxygen both exhibit a mass-to-charge ratio of 16. Detection limits measured at BASE for some relevant species are listed in Table 1.

4. Preliminary Experiments and Implications for Planned Simulation Scenarios

Two preliminary experiments were performed in order to demonstrate the various irradiation and measurement techniques the BASE chamber has to offer. Based on these experiments possible scenarios with application to planetary objects in the solar system and exoplanets are listed.

4.1. Experiment 1: Electron irradiation of methane

Prior to the experiment an extensive cleaning protocol was applied. Subsequently, the chamber was refilled with $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mbar of methane in a dynamic mode. The electron gun was directly interfaced with the BASE chamber. Continuous sampling of the atmosphere within the chamber was carried out with the quadrupole mass spectrometer (QMS).

Given that the BASE chamber was dynamically operated, methane replenishment occurred continuously, ensuring a constant methane concentration inside the chamber. To compensate for minor pressure differences

Settings	
Temperature	298 K
Pressure	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mbar
Mode	Dynamic
Sample	CH_4 (100%)
Irradiation	Electrons

inside the chamber, each spectrum was normalized to the total ion count (TIC normalization) as explained in [48]. Starting with a dark (no electron irradiation) period, the gas was sampled for more than twenty hours. Sampling pure methane shows a specific fragmentation pattern in the mass spectrum, with the parent peak at a mass-to-charge ratio 16. Once stable conditions were reached, the electron gun was turned on (100 μA , 5000 eV electron energy at the source) and the sample irradiated for a day. Figure (4) summarises the progression of m/z 13, where irradiation led to a rapid rise in the normalised ion current from about 0.021 to about 0.023. After turning the electron gun off, the mass spectrum relaxed back towards the dark sample conditions again.

Figure 4: Ion current at mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) 13 normalized to the total ion count (TIC) in each mass spectrum, Blue Line: Progression of m/z ratio 13 as measured by the mass spectrometer over time.

Figure 5: Integrated absorption peak of ozone at 254 nm in arbitrary units. Error bars show the uncertainty on the integrated area.

4.2. Experiment 2: Ozone production under enhanced UV conditions

In a second experiment, the ozone production for an Earth surface scenario under enhanced UV conditions was investigated. BASE underwent a thorough cleaning procedure and was refilled to 1 bar of synthetic air (Lindegas, N_2 0.8 vmr, O_2 0.2 vmr, other constituents < 5 ppm) in a static mode.

The air was irradiated with the hydrogen helium lamp and the ozone concentration subsequently quantified using a UV/Vis spectrometer measuring the absorption at 254 nm. Results in Figure (5) suggest a rapid linear production during the first approximately 1000s followed by a less linear

Settings	
Temperature	298 K
Pressure	1000 mbar
Mode	Static
Sample	N_2 (78%) O_2 (21%) Ar (1%)
Irradiation	HHe lamp

production, potentially lowered by a concurrent destruction process thereafter. Analysis of the temporal data series enabled the calculation of the ozone production rate under enhanced UV conditions, yielding a value of $1.6 \cdot 10^{-5} g/s$ in the second regime.

4.3. Planned Simulation Scenarios

BASE is an experimental setup designed for the investigation of various atmospheric layers, including pressure, temperature and gas composition, with applications to planetary objects in the solar system and exoplanets. Here, we present a list of potential scenarios and outline the parameters that can be viably replicated using the BASE chamber.

Atmospheric conditions for modern Earth's atmosphere, enabling validation with atmospheric models of key species in the atmosphere of our own planet is attainable using BASE. The simulation of modified atmospheric conditions, such as methane-enhanced Earth or oxygen elevated Mars-like atmospheres, is well within the capabilities of BASE. Simulating more exotic hydrogen-dominated atmospheres, particularly

with relevance to planetary systems like TRAPPIST, or replicating scenarios with sulfur components is achievable under low-pressure conditions while adhering to safety regulations.

These experiments not only serve to expand our understanding of the chemistry in various atmospheres but also provide essential data that can be employed for testing and refining atmospheric models pertinent to planetary objects within our solar system and beyond.

5. Outlook

The BASE facility was designed to advance our comprehension of atmospheric gas phase chemistry. The preliminary outcomes demonstrate its current capabilities and limitations compared with other chambers. The spectroscopic systems cover a large spectral range from VUV/VIS/NIR and therefore enables us to simultaneously look at a range of differing gas species. The constant gas sampling from the mass spectrometer allows to reach low detection limits for trace gases even in low pressure scenarios. Further improvements of the detection limit with white cells for FT-IR spectroscopy are under construction. In comparison with other simulation chambers the detection limit is currently limited by the physical size and therefore the beam path through the chamber. Choosing a small chamber brings the advantage of a low leak rate and the possibility to fit the set-up inside a glovebox. The possibility to simulate anoxic gas mixtures, very different from our own atmosphere is, in particular, a key feature of our set-up. The unique combination of an electron source alongside a full stellar spectrum is of particular scientific relevance. In addition, the wall properties allow minor sticky species to exhibit a lifetime long enough to study dynamics over several days to weeks.

Figure (6) gives an overview of the current feasibility for the types of atmospheres we plan to simulate with BASE based on future work and the tests performed so far. We anticipate that our research will provide valuable insights into the comprehension of chemical responses within the atmospheres of rocky planets in and beyond the solar system.

Possible Scenarios of atmospheric simulations with BASE

	Earth Surface to Stratopause	Mars Surface	Venus 50 km Altitude	Titan Surface	Exoplanet Atmosphere
Temperature	200 K – 297 K	213 K	300 K	90 K	297 K – 397 K
Pressure	1 mbar – 1013 mbar	6 mbar	500 mbar	1600 mbar	1·10 ⁻⁶ mbar – 1013 mbar
Mode	Static/Dynamic	Static/Dynamic	Static/Dynamic	Static/Dynamic	Static/Dynamic
Composition (vmr)	0.78 N ₂ 0.21 O ₂ 0.02 Ar	0.95 CO ₂ 0.02 N ₂ 0.02 Ar	0.96 CO ₂ 0.03 N ₂ 150 ppm SO ₂	0.95 N ₂ 0.05 CH ₄ 0.001 H ₂	N ₂ , O ₂ , CO ₂ , CH ₄ , H ₂ O, Ar, NH ₃ , H ₂ , SO ₂ ,
Irradiation	Solarsimulator H/He Lamp Flow Lamp Electron Gun	Solarsimulator H/He Lamp Flow Lamp Electron Gun			
Possible Topics	Ozone	Potential Methane in Mars Atmosphere	SO ₂ destruction through UV irradiation	Photochemical Tholin production	H ₂ , H ₂ O or CO ₂ atmospheres

Figure 6: Possible Scenarios of atmospheric simulations with BASE including an indication of the current feasibility of planned experimental parameters. Green: Feasible, Yellow: Feasible for specific parameters under limited conditions, Red: Currently not available.

Composition in volume mixing ratio based on [49] for Mars, [50] for Titan and [51] for Venus.

The flow lamp and the electron gun are available for all scenarios under the premise of potential set-up adaption such as the inclusion of a differential pumping system or additional windows.

Trace gases as low as 0.0002 volume mixing ratio can in principle be included in any atmospheric composition. In this case experiments are mainly limited by the detection limits for such low concentrations. Toxic and flammable gases are subjected to Health and Safety regulations. Potential scenarios must be analysed in case-by-case studies.

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